

Some proposals for planning, management and control of long-term programs¹ and projects

Dott. R. Morelli – IEng MIET; TCM A AICE/ICEC .

SUMMARY: This article deals with some methods, outlined in the course of concrete works, partly presented in a more extensive way in the meetings of the AICE Days 2017 and 2018 and available among the Proceedings of said Days or in works published on the AICE website (<https://www.aice-it.org/it>). They are taken up here and logically interconnected in unitary form for discussion. In one case, in the first part, from the trend of the "historical" data series of expected and actual disbursements, it is proposed to obtain two functions whose intersection provides the best estimate, at the time of the analysis, of the time and cost of completing a program or project. In another case, the second part, it is proposed to integrate times and costs into a single progress parameter, since both times and costs are always two external constraints contractually given for the execution of a project.

Anyone who has an understanding of industrial business, or knows programming techniques, or has prepared and managed a relevant project or contract, is well aware that on a cost-time graph (see Fig. 0) the area subtended by the curve representing the outlay (in the jargon an "S" curve, even if the shape can be different) assumes the sense of a generic "qualitative" index of financial burden of the program, project or contract, depending on the case.

This financial burden is particularly relevant in long-term programs, projects or contracts. In these cases, such a generic index can be the basis for providing useful starting points for important considerations of other kinds as well, some of which are proposed below, as both times and costs are always two external constraints contractually given for the execution of a project, a program, a contract. In order to better clarify the matter, the various diagrams represented in Fig. 1 below can be examined as an introduction:

¹ By program, excluding the cases in which a time schedule is meant, we assume a set of several projects integrated with each other (not only logically) which constitute a *unicum* for the achievement of a specific objective. Individually or in an integrated way, the projects are the subject of various forms of contract between the parties involved.

Fig. 1

They all refer to different payment options for an order with duration (t) and total disbursement (P). Case (a) presents a full advance payment at the start of the works; case (d) represents a totally deferred payment at the end of the works; cases (b) and (c), on the other hand, are intermediate situations between the two extreme cases mentioned.

It can be seen that the areas subtended by the diagrams grow from zero in (d) up to the maximum in (a), so it seems legitimate to say that small areas indicate convenience for the client, vice versa, large areas indicate convenience for the supplier or contractor. In other words, the area subtended by the disbursement diagram can be an index, for the client, of the financial burden of the order, while for the contractor or supplier it can represent an index of the financing of the order which should be temporarily covered in view of the final profit.

Situations of equity, even if this term is always the subject of ideological asymmetries, are reached when the real trends in disbursements by the customer closely match the real trends in disbursements by the supplier or contractor made during the implementation.

In any case, the area alone of a disbursement diagram is wholly inadequate to be used as an element for quantitative evaluations. In fact, by way of example, from Fig. 2.1 and Fig. 2.2 it can be understood that, even with the same underlying area, situations (a) and (b) give rise to significantly different financial findings, as identical areas are differently distant from the vertical axis have different financial content.

Fig.2.1

Fig.2.2

This does not mean, however, that the financial meaning attributable to the area underlying the disbursement diagram can include not only a "heuristic" value, but also a practical application value, as will emerge below.

I. First Part

Experience shows that large multi-year programs and projects, typical in the institutional field, are rarely launched with a project already defined and computable analytically, but usually there is a "meta-project", poorly defined, except in terms of objectives or in very general terms, on the basis of which a sort of initial estimating planning takes place, usually on an overall analogical basis or for individual large parts. That is, for example, similar cases are sought, even on larger and smaller scales, and costs and times are estimated by analytically taking into account the "scale effects". Nevertheless, however accurate the estimation process may be and however scrupulous the risk-analysis of cost and time overrun risk may be carried out, in the end, in concrete terms, an estimate remains an estimate and can only constitute a general but approximate reference, subject to necessary modifications. On the other hand, truly analogous or similar projects are always quite rare and difficult to find. The returns of experience and data on them are often late and affected by economic issues (e.g. baselines references, exchange and inflation rates), confidentiality (security and market issues), commercial (niche vs. competition), industrial, technological, environmental and socio-political, that more and more show their great variability and incidence. Therefore, in reality - during the execution, due to the effect of the initial approximations - repeated planning are recorded as the project progresses, accompanied by an increase in the costs and the times initially foreseen. From such re-planning, historical series of data can emerge that are useful for an analytical examination of trends (trends).

Precisely in multi-year programs, a whole-life cost of project (or the amount of other whole-life resources dedicated to it) is one of the most important parameters to be identified in the planning phase (or during subsequent re-planning). However, the lifetime cost, in some very large and long-term projects - e.g. of an infrastructural type (for the construction of railways, motorways, or networks in general, etc.), or for the dismantling of large dismissed industrial projects (e.g. nuclear power plants and plants, or the restoration of vast heavily compromised and polluted areas) - not only does it vary (usually increasing) over the course of the project itself, but it can involve the establishment of a structured team or even a full-fledged program management company. In these cases, a systematic and periodic follow-up activity is carried out, reviewing the planning, including the time schedule and the whole life cost which shows its trend line over time. Precisely in these particular cases, trend analyzes on the resources allocated to the project (e.g. historical series of disbursements foreseen in subsequent re-planning during construction) and those actually used can be a useful forecasting aid in project monitoring and control themselves.

Fig. 3 – Trend Analysis during performance (e.g. construction) for the purpose of forecasting times and costs "to finish"

The convergence point of the trend line of whole-life resources with the trend line of resources actually used gradually along the various implementation phases, takes on not only value of reference for the

actual progress of the project, but also predictive value on the possible end of the project itself and on the amount of resources required (see Fig. 3). The trend procedure conducted graphically or analytically therefore focuses the monitoring and control of the project on the point of convergence P_n . The geometric procedure of intersection of two trend lines on a plane (x,y) identifies the coordinates of the point P_n through the following system formed by the equations of the two trend lines found (e.g. with the method of least squares or with the partial average procedure):

$$\begin{cases} y = a_1 + b_1 x \\ y = a_2 + b_2 x \end{cases} \quad 3.1$$

It goes without saying that in those cases in which the slopes of the two lines are such as to diverge (i.e. the average rate of increase in whole-life costs is greater than the disbursement rate for the realization of the project) it means that the project is out of control and you risk never seeing its implementation. If the two trend functions were not linear, but were two different generic functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ the reasoning would be completely identical except that the system would take the form:

$$\begin{cases} y = f(x) \\ y = g(x) \end{cases} \quad 3.2$$

Finally, in cases in which the management of the long-term project is entrusted to a real management company, it must be borne in mind that construction delays (e.g. $\Delta t = \text{Delta } t$ in the Fig.3), during which no progress of the project produced or it is produced in a modest way, they automatically transform into a rise in whole life costs due to the general and operating costs that the company itself (or the responsible team) requires "for functioning", as it is clearly visible from the red box area in Fig. 3, which represents a real "loss" (additional cost) for the project. Therefore, it is not just a question of the usual increase in general costs; to which even these costs are subjected over time. Finally, it is worth emphasizing that the trend proposed here is all the more accurate and reliable the more data are available, which happens in the advanced implementation phase of the program or project. A use of this methodology right from the initial stages, when the available data are still scarce, although it can produce much more approximate results and "alarms", is nonetheless recommended, since it alerts the sense of managerial control right away.

II. Second Part

Usually, beside employed capital efficiency aspects, there is a "compulsory" feature - also of an institutional and/or contractual nature - of management control in relation to the values of times, costs, and resources in general, initially planned. The mandatory value of management control also arises from the fact that for the client, be it institutional, public or private, during ordinary management, not only the total cost of the project (C_t), as well as the final time (t_f) within which it must be terminated (that is, it is the immovable position of P_0 in Fig.4), but the shape of the disbursement curve must also be invariant, whether it be "S" shaped or not. Naturally, if the deviations revealed during performance were not recoverable, it would necessarily lead to extraordinary management and therefore to re-planning and re-scheduling (from P_0 to P_0), evidently followed by a re-contractualization. Perhaps it should be emphasized that at each rescheduling the point (P_0) can be approximately determined with the trend method illustrated in *Part I*.

“Economic and Temporal Progress Indexes” are not adequate:

“Economic Progress” at generic time $t_x = (C_x/C_t)$ is not representative of real progress.

“Temporal Progress” at generic time $t_x = (t_x/t_f)$ is not representative of real progress.

Furthermore consider:

$$\int_{t_0}^{t_f} S(t) \neq \int_{t_0}^{t_f} S'(t) \quad 2.1$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\int_{t_0}^{t_f} S'(t) - \int_{t_0}^{t_f} S(t)}{\int_{t_0}^{t_f} S(t)} \quad 2.2$$

Fig. 4 - Review of planning at time t_x due to overruns of times and/or costs

The recent ICMS² Standards still seem not widespread and the traditional concepts and procedures of the Earned Value type - often considered unwieldy - do not yet seem to have sufficiently permeated the public and private procurement sectors³.

The formulation of an application proposal for an "Integrated Work Progress Indicator" in the institutional, public or private sphere, appears most appropriate, not only for the contractual effects to which a state of progress is usually connected. Such a proposal arises from the fact that it is not unusual, in some large projects, especially public ones, to give managerial meaning to the concepts of economic progress index and time progress index, defined as the ratio between the actual values (of times or costs separately) at a certain time and those of the budget whole life or total lifetime value of the program. The simple time lapsing and the increase in actual disbursements, or their singular relationships with respect to the contractual values, are not by themselves - especially if taken individually - a sign of the progress of the project. Therefore, the management control procedures of an institutional project, through the analysis of deviations from the planned, must always have a mandatory-priority value, but must be based on indicators representative of reality as much as possible. It is worth pointing out that if the increase in the final balances (costs or times) accrued in a given period are equivalent to the increases (overruns) in the total cost or total time to finish, the actual economic or time progress, in that period, is eroded and can become substantially null.⁴

² See for instance: <https://www.aice-it.org/it/area-download/icms>

³ See for instance: <http://www.pmtsi.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/2020-01-25-Earned-Value-Questo-Sconosciuto.pdf>

⁴ By program, excluding the cases in which a time schedule is meant, we assume a set of several projects integrated with each other, not only logically, which constitute a unicum for the achievement of a specific objective. Individually or in an integrated way, the projects are the subject of various forms of contract between the parties involved.

Fig. 5 – Example of lack of representativeness of economic or temporal progress as defined above, as much more as in vicinity of the conditions [$(t_a - t_i) = (t_s - t_f)$; $(\Delta C_a = \Delta C_t)$] .

In other words, in Fig.5, having assumed period $(t_a - t_i)$ as unitary, the incremental ratio of the final balances is the increase ΔC_a . In case forecast conditions arise during the period for which the lifetime cost increases by an increment ΔC_t exactly equal to the increment in the final balance ΔC_a it appears that on the basis of the linear trend it is as if another period of equal (unitary) entity were added at the end from t_f to t_s . This, in practice, erodes the value of the economic progress (making it practically nil, not only in the case of a linear trend).

Therefore, it appears that, at any moment of project execution, it is more significant and correct, to determine a more objective and realistic state of progress, referring to another work progress indicator formulated differently, and diverse from simplistic economic or temporal progress indexes.

Furthermore, in comparing different plans⁵, without the definition of an appropriate, independent and different work progress index (based, for example, on man hours or physically objective quantities) it may be misleading to assume only the aforementioned "progress" on costs or times, or their indicators and values as elements of comparative judgment or as representative elements of the progress of the project program. For example, it is difficult to express an exact, comparable and truthful judgment on the progress (physical, temporal or economic) achieved in each year of implementation, in the different periods (two years, five years, etc.) and throughout life, when there are continuous changes in re-planning; in this way it is possible to "lose" the notion or even to no longer consider the true initial reference. For this reason, an appropriate reflection is proposed if :

- in order to compare among different plans or projects, it may be more significant (together with other traditional indexes , such as: economic and temporal dimension, NPV, Breakeven Point, Pay Back Period, Debt Service Coverage Ratio, etc.) refer even to the area subtended by the "S" curve of the disbursement; and

⁵ By plan here is meant the program and its time schedule elevated to value; so that each program activity and related time schedule (bar chart) have got a distribution of disbursement allocated along the time axis.

- it may be appropriate an index (ρ) as an integrated cost-time progress (as per 6.1 – Fig. 6 below), to be evaluated from time to time and case by case; and
- the index (ρ) may be the ratio between the area under the cost-time "S" curve relating to the actual disbursement up to a given moment and the area under the cost-time "S" curve relating to total costs and times, i.e. final balances and forecasts from that moment on, as it results from the re-planning up to that moment.

Referring to the following Fig.N.6 we would have :

$$\rho = \frac{(\text{Area under the cost-time "S" curve relating to the actual disbursement up to } t_a)}{(\text{Area under the cost-time "S" curve relating to the Actual Disbursement up to } t_a) + (\text{Area under the cost-time "S" curve relating to the Estimate Disbursement up to } t_f)} \quad 6.1$$

Fig.6 – Integrated disbursement curve: Actual up to t_a + Estimate Re-planned at time t_a up to t_f

Such a progress indicator, freeing itself more from the intrinsic unpredictability of variations in the forecast values of total times and lifetime costs of the project, seems to take on a more adequate representation of reality, since any variation (even simultaneous) of times and costs is immediately reflected on the progress, which therefore becomes more "stable and reliable" to inform management of the actual status of a project.

For application to specific cases, the following are distinguished:

Case A - The ideal case of functions with continuous behavior;

Case B - The concrete case of functions with step behavior;

which are illustrated below.

Fig. 7 Case A

With reference to Fig. 7 - Case A on the side, by Lagrange's (or Mean) theorem we have:

$$Q = \frac{\int_{t_0}^{t_a} k(t)}{\int_{t_0}^{t_a} k(t) + \int_{t_a}^{t_f} f(t)} = \frac{M_{k(t)}(t_a - t_0)}{M_{k(t)}(t_a - t_0) + M_{f(t)}(t_f - t_a)} \quad 7.2.A$$

(M... = Mean)

Fig.7 – Case B

With reference to Fig. 7 – Case B on the side, we have:

$$Q = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^a k(t_i)(x_i)}{\sum_{i=0}^a k(t_i)(x_i) + \sum_{i=a}^f f(t_i)(x_i)} \quad 7.2.B$$

$x_i = (t_i - t_{i-1})$ generic time interval
 $f(t_i)$ = average value in the generic time interval x_i
 $k(t_i)$ = average value in the generic time interval x_i

Usually you don't get to have a mathematical function (perhaps through "best fitting" operations), but data in a table as in Tab. 1 below; for example with costs and times, in the form of a historical series of "cumulative values", divided between "actual values" (here, up to 2017 - in blue) and "estimated values" (in red) of a project started in the year 2000 and expected to finish in 2034.

With them it is possible to perform a calculation with constant time intervals through the summation method [formula (7.2.B)] illustrated previously.

Perhaps in an era where quantum computers are envisaged it may appear anachronistic, but both in the First and in the Second Part, it is only apparently a question of calculations that may seem complicated (given the symbols of integrals and summations), because if all the available and necessary data are reported for graphing on a graph paper sheet (now obsolete tool), the trends can be easily performed with ruler and set square, while the calculation of the areas is reduced to a trivial count of squares (see Fig.8).

	SOMMATORIE	ANNO	Abbreviazione	DATI DISPONIBILI (Costo M€)	Ipotesi Conc. nel 2009
C o n s u m t i v i c u m u l a t i		2000	0	0,00	
		2001	1	0,00	
		2002	2	5,79	
		2003	3	11,58	
		2004	4	17,37	
		2005	5	23,16	
		2006	6	28,95	
		2007	7	34,74	
		2008	8	40,53	
		2009	9	46,31	
		2010	10	59,63	
		2011	11	77,82	
		2012	12	99,45	
		2013	13	120,39	
		2014	14	158,11	
		2015	15	201,07	
		2016	16	234,44	
	1428,24	2017	17	268,90	1266,12
P r e v e n t i v i c u m u l a t i		2018	18	308,92	
		2019	19	364,49	
		2020	20	436,01	
		2021	21	535,72	
		2022	22	596,17	
		2023	23	644,40	
		2024	24	678,80	
		2025	25	692,71	
		2026	26	706,63	
		2027	27	720,54	
	2028	28	734,45		
	2029	29	737,08		
	2030	30	739,71		
	2031	31	742,34		
	2032	32	744,97		
	2033	33	747,60		
	2034	34	750,23		
	10880,78	2035	35	750,23	10880,78
		2036	36	750,23	
	12309,02	TOTALI		12309,02	12146,90
	11,60%	Integrated Progress Index			10,42%

Tab. 1

III. Third Part - Further reminders

In the light of the contents set out above, the close connection between the chronological programs (e.g. time schedule) characterizing each realization and the related financial burden can be recalled, especially in multi-year programs. In this connection, well known to those involved in planning, two main planning criteria are to be distinguished:

- a) a criterion of maximum advance, consisting in the allocation "as soon as possible", on the time axis, of the "floating" activities⁶ (i.e. not those activities on the critical path, where every activity has got zero "float") and therefore with the possibility to be moved up to some extent on the axis;
- b) a criterion of maximum delay, consisting in the allocation "at the latest", on the axis of time, of the same "floating" activities.

A clarification of the topic is possible by examining Fig. 9, where the critical path is highlighted by the sequence of critical activities and the slack activities are allocated differently, depending on the criterion adopted.

Fig. 9

However, it must be remembered that the indiscriminate adoption of the criterion of maximum delay, if on one hand reduces the financial burdens, allowing the economic commitment on the floating activities as late as possible, on the other it makes the program hypercritical, increasing possibility of delay for the entire planned implementation if even one of the theoretically floating and practically criticized activities is delayed. For this reason it is argued that the 'at the latest' approach in programming should be excluded for programs which place a high value on the ultimate goal – e.g. the maintenance or construction programs of electricity generation plants, the completion of which is linked to the start-up of the plant, not only for commercial considerations; which is why in these cases the "as soon as possible" programming approach is adopted, leaving its opposite limited almost exclusively to applications for financial reasons, typical of the long term. If we now consider that each program activity is (theoretically) linked to one or more payments, which can be hypothesized to be allocated differently along the entire program and/or the activity itself, it becomes clear how each program, as well as each program-line is characterized by its own disbursement curve. The criterion of the maximum deferment brings payments, for non-critical activities, closer to the final part of the program, resulting in a reduction of the area covered by the disbursement curve. The opposite effect is produced by the maximum advance criterion.

⁶ Float (also known as slack) is the amount of time by which the start of an activity can be delayed without delaying the project completion time.

It is quite clear that the financial aspects - and therefore the associated risk - are all the more relevant in case of:

- high economic and temporal dimensions (typical aspect of the long term);
- high recourse to external financing rather than the use of own capital or equity (today more and more often also financed!);
- high presence of foreign currency (which introduces exchange rate risk or instability of other economies) or presence of "common currency" typical of free trade areas;
- the conditions for repaying the loan are stringent and those for granting it are looser (as the sub-prime crisis has shown);

all factors that can suggest an increasing risk (exponentially!) with the increase of the time dimension and which push us to consider more and more, in the initial planning phase, "the area under the curve of disbursements" and to prepare realistic and effective management, monitoring and control tools, necessary during the long implementation of a program or project of the case considered here. Any costly accelerations of the program, which should obviously concern the critical path and the activities that constitute it, implying an advance of payments, should lead to an evaluation, among other things, also of the financial aspects to ensure that the benefits resulting from the acceleration do not are lower than the costs to achieve it.

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